

SCALE EFFECT IN FATIGUE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS*

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Introduction

It is known that the endurance limit (fatigue limit) of a material under fatigue loading decreases as the size of the specimen increases [1]. A large amount of test data for metals is available, and many theories have been offered, but none of the theories have been satisfactory. For instance, in [2] it was found that for an Al-Cu alloy the fatigue limit of a large sheet (230 mm width) is only 50% of that of a small sheet (19 mm width). In contrast, the fatigue limit for corresponding mild steel specimens showed that the large sheet has 85% the fatigue limit of the small sheet. Among factors mentioned that may contribute to the scale effect include maximum stress gradient, heating of large specimen, surface stress, etc. No statistical theory was mentioned.

Recently, the detrimental effect of size in composite material has been recognized and attempts by the statistical approach have been proposed. For instance, in Ref. [3] and [4] the ratio of strength of two specimens was assumed equal to the ratio of their volumes under stress. This, in essence, is considering that all defects or micro-flaws are arranged in series, and the weakest link breaks the chain.

The concept of in-series and in-parallel arrangement in statistical studies is not new. In classical reliability analysis the series-parallel arrangements are often used for engineering systems, see for instance Shooman [5]. These arrangements have also been assumed, sometimes implicitly, in studying the strength of structures and materials, see [6]. It seems that they have not been used to study the scale effect of fatigue life.

The goal of the present study is to obtain basic understanding of scale effect in the fatigue life of composite material structures. This basic understanding may be used to develop scaling laws such that the service life of a full size structure may be predicted from tests of small size models or specimens.

The full size structure is considered as consisting of n "elements". These elements may be statistically in-series, or in-parallel, or a combination of these two. If the whole structure fails when any one of the elements fails, then these elements are considered to be in-series. This is also

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known as the weakest-link theory. On the other hand, if after one element fails, the rest of the elements can still carry the total load, the elements are considered in-parallel; this is equivalent to a bundle of loose filaments, and amenable to the bundle theory analysis.

If the strength, or fatigue life, of the element has a small statistical scatter, or large Weibull shape parameter, then the mean strength or life of the n-element structure is not too much different from that of the element. This is true for both in-series and in-parallel arrangements. However, if the scatter is large, which is the case for fatigue life of composites, the n-element structure has much shorter life than the element.

To substantiate this in-series/in-parallel model in relation to fatigue of composites, we have selected as the basic element a composite specimen with a single drilled hole, (Fig. 1). By arranging a number of holes in different arrays, we may accomplish in-series and in-parallel models. The present paper reports the results of the basic element and the three elements in-series cases, as shown in Fig. 1. This drilled-hole element was selected because it represents the rivet or bolt holes in actual structures, and it can be arranged in simple in-series/in-parallel models. Fatigue properties of riveted and bolted joints in composite panels are reported in [7] and [8].

The specimens were loaded in static compression and constant amplitude compression fatigue. The compression loading is used because it is known that graphite/epoxy composites have a shorter compression fatigue life as compared to tension fatigue, see Refs. [9] and [10]. The fatigue tests were at a constant amplitude of $\sigma_{\max} = 0$, $\sigma_{\min} = -2800$ lbf (-12.50 kN) ($R = -\infty$). This maximum compression stress is approximately 74% of the mean static strength. Relevant properties and dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig. 1.

The in-parallel model of scale effect is in the development stage. Pertinent material concerning this model and its verification is contained in Ref. [11].

Equations for the In-Series Model

In the traditional weakest link concept in material strength, the basic "link" is a flaw in the material, see for instance Ref. [12]. The present in-series model is of the same principle as the weakest link, except we use a structural "element" as a link. This element can be of a size in the same order of magnitude of the total structure. It is well-known that the weakest link concept can be described in mathematical statistics by the extreme value theory, see for instance, Ref. [13] and [14]. We shall summarize the results for elements of Weibull distribution.

Consider a basic element of Weibull distribution, with a density function

$$f(x) = \frac{\alpha(x-x_0)^{\alpha-1}}{\beta^\alpha} \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x-x_0}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (1)$$

and a cumulative distribution function (CDF)

$$F_X(x) = P(X \leq x) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x-x_0}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (2)$$

A. Geometry

B. Properties

Material:	Hercules AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy
Layers:	12
Layup:	$[\pm 45, 0_2, \bar{+} 45]_S$

Figure 1. Specimen Geometry and Properties

where x = strength or life, x_0 = position parameter, α = shape parameter, and β = scale parameter. Then the CDF of an n -element in-series specimen can be shown to be

$$F_{X_n}(x) = P(X_n \leq x) = 1 - [1 - P(X \leq x)]^n \quad (3)$$

The density function, $f_n(x)$, of the n -element specimen is then

$$f_n(x) = \frac{\alpha(x-x_0)^{\alpha-1}}{(\beta/n)^{1/\alpha} \alpha} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x-x_0}{\beta/n^{1/\alpha}} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (4)$$

Comparing Eq. (4) with Eq. (1), we conclude that the shape parameter α , and position parameter x_0 , of the n -element in-series model are identical to those of the basic element; the scale parameter β is reduced from that of the basic element by a factor $n^{1/\alpha}$.

The mean strength or life is given by

$$\mu = \beta \Gamma \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \right) + x_0 \quad (5)$$

If the position parameter is equal to zero then the mean of the n -element in-series, μ_n is related to the basic element mean, μ by

$$\frac{\mu_n}{\mu} = \left(\frac{1}{n} \right)^{1/\alpha} \quad (6)$$

The decrease of the mean is a function of the shape parameter, as well as the number of elements, n . For a value of $\alpha = 2$, the strength or life decreases a great deal; for $n = 100$, the strength of the in-series combination is only 10% of the basic element. For a large value of b , however, the decrease in strength is not too much. For instance, for $n = 100$ and $b = 30$, μ_n is 86% of μ .

Since for composite materials the shape parameter for static strength is between 10 to 30, and for fatigue life it is between 1 to 3, it can be seen that the size effect is more serious in fatigue life than in static strength, if the elements are in-series. In other words, a long coupon has almost the same static strength as a short element, but has only a small fraction of the fatigue life of the element.

Static and Fatigue Experiments

To verify the in-series model a number of static and fatigue tests were performed using both the basic element and the in-series specimen.

Specimens

All specimens used for this study were cut from a Hercules AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite plate prepared at the Naval Air Development Center, Warminster, Pa. The plate consisted of 12 layers following a layup of $[\pm 45, 0_2, \mp 45]_S$. The overall measurements of the plate were 24 by 34 inches (610 by 860 mm) with an average thickness of 0.072 inch, (1.83 mm). End tabs were cut from plates prepared of 3M Scotchply 1003 fiberglass/epoxy with a layup of $[0_2, 90, 0_2, 90, 0_2, 90, 0_2]$. The thickness of the plates were 0.080 inch, (2.03 mm).

The basic element was a 1 x 6 inch (25.4x152.4 mm) strip with a central 1/4 inch (6.4 mm) hole. The in-series specimen had the same overall dimensions, but with three 1/4 inch (6.4 mm) holes. End tabs of length 1 1/2 inch (38.1 mm) were applied to the ends of both sides of each specimen. (See cutting procedure for method of application). The dimensions for the basic element and the in-series specimen are given in Fig. 1. The portion between the end tabs was considered as the test section.

The plate was cut into test specimens by means of a 5 13/16 inch (147.6 mm) diameter diamond saw blade mounted on a Sundstrand Rigidmil. The blade was run at 715 rpm with a table feed rate of 1 inch (25.4 mm) per minute. The first step in the cutting procedure consisted of cutting the plate into 6 1/2 x 10 inch (165.1x254.0 mm) sections such that the 0° fibers were parallel to the shorter edge. Next 1 1/2 x 10 inch (38.1x254.0 mm) end tab strips of 0.080 inch (2.03 mm) thickness were bonded to both sides of the sections, 1/4 inch (6.4 mm) from each of the 10 inch (254.0 mm) edges. The bonding agent used was Ecobond 51 combined with Catalyst #9, both manufactured by Emerson and Cuming Inc. These sections were then squared off and cut down to 6 x 10 inch (152.4x254.0 mm) by taking off 1/4 inch (6.4 mm) along each of the 10 inch (254.0 mm) edges. Next the sections were cut into 6 x 1 inch (152.4x25.4 mm) strips. Each section yielded 9 of these strips.

Specimen holes were drilled with straight fluted solid carbide drill bits manufactured by Cleveland Twist Drill Co. First a pilot hole was made in the specimen with a 1/8 inch (3.2 mm) bit. This was enlarged with a 1/4 inch (6.4 mm) bit. The bits show no noticeable wear after drilling in excess of 200 holes.

After cutting and drilling the completed specimens were stored at room temperature and humidity until testing.

Testing Apparatus

All testing was performed on an Instron Model 1230 Dynamic Test Machine equipped with a Model 836 remote control panel, a Model 602 load and stroke controller panel, and a Model 860A function generator. This testing machine has the capacity of $\pm 10,000$ lbf (± 40 kN) load which can be applied in the form of a sine input, triangular input, square input, or ramp input. The maximum reliable frequency for operating this machine is 30 Hz. The Instron Wedge Action Gripping Jaws were used in conjunction with our own gripping and anti-buckling guide system (to be described later). For static tests a Hewlett Packard Model 7045A X-Y Recorder was used. Additional Equipment included a Tektronix 7623A Storage Oscilloscope and a Keithley Instruments 160 Digital Multimeter.

A method for gripping the specimen and for preventing buckling during loading was designed, and a sectioned assembly of this apparatus is shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen the bottom and top grips are held in place by the Instron Jaws. The gaps between the jaws and the grips are filled with shim stock. The top grip is stationary and the two vertical runners are bolted to it. The bottom grip is free to ride up and down in these runners. The applied load is transmitted by the actuator arm of the Instron through the bottom Instron Jaw to the bottom grip. The frictional force between the bottom grip and the vertical runners was found to be negligible (less than 10 lbf or 44 N). The anti-buckling guide also fits in the runners and is free to move up and down. The runners insure correct alignment of the top and bottom grips and the anti-buckling guide. Hence the test specimen will have no initial crookedness. The clearance between the anti-buckling guide faces and the specimen surfaces of course varies from specimen to specimen but on the average is 0.003 inch, (0.08 mm). The section view shows that the

Figure 2 Sectioned Assembly, Specimen Gripping Anti-Buckling Device

specimen's ends are in contact with the grip floors. This insures that the load is applied on the ends of and along the axis of the test specimen. The figure also indicates that the rear gripping plates are held in place by 1/4 20 Allen screws inserted through the front grips. The rear anti-buckling guide plate is held to the front anti-buckling guide by four screws.

Detail drawings of the grips and anti-buckling guide are presented in Ref. [11].

Testing Procedures

All tests were run at room temperature with ambient humidity. In order to reduce friction between the specimen and the anti-buckling guide, a thin coating of Molykote 44 grease, a heat stable silicone lubricant, was applied to the contact surfaces of the guides.

For static tests the specimen was secured in the grips and the back of the anti-buckling guide was screwed in position. A compressive load of 10 lbf (40 N) was applied to the specimen and then the screws holding the backs of the grips and anti-buckling guide were torqued tight. The load was then released. Next, operating in the stroke mode and using the ramp input a compressive load was applied to failure. The failure load was recorded on the X-Y plotter.

For fatigue tests, the specimen was secured in the grips and the back of the anti-buckling guide was screwed in place (hand tight). Small pieces of styrofoam were placed between the guide and the grips in order to damp out any vibration. Operating in the load mode a compressive load was gradually applied up to 100 lbf (440 N). Then the screws holding the grips and guide in place were torqued tight. The load was then increased slowly until the desired mean load was obtained. In the present test, the mean load is -1400 lbf (-6.23 kN). A sine wave cycling of the applied load with an amplitude of 1400 lbf (6.23 kN) was then started. For the first 10 cycles a frequency of 0.01 Hz was used. During this time the loading was rechecked with the use of the digital multimeter and oscilloscope to make sure that the specimen did not go into tension and the load was cycling between 0 and -2800 lbf (-12.50 kN). The frequency was then gradually and slowly increased to 5 Hz. Periodically the loading was checked with the oscilloscope and screws retorqued as necessary. The specimen was run to failure and fatigue life was recorded in cycles by the control panel counter.

Experimental Results

This section presents the static and fatigue test results for the basic element and the three-in-series specimen. All specimens failed through a drilled hole. For each test, the ultimate load, or the fatigue life of each specimen is given in tabular form. The sample means and sample standard deviations are also calculated from the following formulas

$$\text{Sample mean} = \bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Sample standard deviation} = s = \left[\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where n is the total number of specimens tested in each case.

Table I. Static Strength and Fatigue Life of the Basic Element, Graphite/Epoxy [$\pm 45, 0_2, + 45$]_s

a. Ultimate Static Compression Load, lbf (kN), (12 specimens)				
2950 (13.12)	3600 (16.01)	3900 (17.35)	4350 (19.35)	
3100 (13.79)	3630 (16.15)	3900 (17.35)	4600 (20.46)	
3250 (14.46)	3770 (16.77)	3940 (17.55)	4650 (20.68)	
$\bar{x} = 3800$ (16.90)				
$s = 550$ (2.45)				
b. Compression Fatigue Life, Cycles, Max. Compression Load = 74% Basic Element Mean Static Strength, R = $-\infty$, Frequency = 5 Hz (10 specimens)				
17230	26230	78750	107880	127540
20010	49460	83300	112120	128780
$\bar{x} = 75130$				
$s = 44200$				

Table Ia presents the static strength measured in lbf (kN) for the basic elements. The sample mean and sample standard deviation are 3800 and 550 lbf (16.90 and 2.45 kN) respectively. Table Ib gives the fatigue life measured in cycles for the basic elements. The maximum compressive load to which each element was subjected was 2800 lbf (74% of mean static) while the minimum load was 0. The mean and standard deviation of the basic element fatigue life were 75,130 and 44,200 cycles respectively.

Table II. Static Strength and Fatigue Life of the Three-In-Series Specimen, Graphite/Epoxy [$\pm 45, 0_2, + 45$]_s

a. Ultimate Static Compression Load, lbf (kN), (10 specimens)				
3000 (13.34)T*	3260 (14.50)T	3450 (15.35)B	3660 (16.28)B	
3150 (14.01)B	3400 (15.12)B	3600 (16.01)B		
3150 (14.01)T	3400 (15.12)M	3600 (16.01)T		
$\bar{x} = 3370$ (14.99)				
$s = 220$ (1.00)				
b. Compression Fatigue Life, Cycles, Max. Compression Load = 74% Basic Element Mean Static Strength, R = $-\infty$, Frequency = 5 Hz (9 specimens)				
2090 M	15270 B	19990 M	29950 M	47690 B
5040 T	16090 B	24700 B	32740 B	
$\bar{x} = 21510$				
$s = 14200$				
* Failed hole location, T = top, M = middle, B = bottom.				

Table IIa shows the static strength measured in lbf (kN) for the three-in-series specimens. Also the position of the failure is given. The sample mean is 3370 lbf (14.99 kN) and the standard deviation is 220 lbf (1.00 kN). Table IIb presents the fatigue life in cycles and the position of the failed hole for each of the three-in-series specimens subjected to the same loading conditions as the basic element fatigue specimens. Here, $\bar{x} = 21,510$ cycles, and $s = 14,200$ cycles.

We see that in the static case the mean strength of the three-in-series specimen is 89% of the basic element mean strength. However, the mean life of the three-in-series specimen is 29% of the basic element mean life. It is evident that the in-series configuration greatly reduces the fatigue life, but has a much less effect on the static strength.

Ref. [11] presents some additional test data and discussion for specimens with different geometry.

Parameter Estimations

Interval Estimation for the Mean

According to the in-series model, the life and strength of the three-in-series specimen should be lower than those of the basic element. From the data in the previous section, it can be seen that indeed the sample mean life and mean strength for the three-in-series are both lower than the corresponding basic element values. The sample mean values, however, are random variables, dependent on the sample size, and by themselves have less statistical significance. In order to establish a confidence level on the hypothesis that the three-in-series and basic element specimens were from two different populations and that the three-in-series case has a lower mean value, we shall make interval estimations for the means.

We shall assume that the random variable

$$t_{n-1} = \frac{(\bar{x} - \mu) \sqrt{n}}{s} \quad (9)$$

has the Student-t distribution with n-1 degree of freedom. Strictly speaking, this is true only when the population is normal. For practical purposes, it is a good enough approximation for non-normal distributions, [15]. Based on this assumption, we have estimated the confidence intervals for all four cases, and listed the results in Table III.

Table III. Confidence Intervals for Basic and Three-In-Series Specimens

a. Fatigue Life

Specimen	Confidence Interval for Mean Life, Cycles	% Confidence
Basic	[43510, 106750]	95%
3-in-series	[10600, 32420]	95%

b. Static Strength

Specimen	Confidence Intervals for Mean Strength		% Confidence
	lbf	kN	
Basic	[3520, 4090]	[15.7, 18.2]	90%
	[3460, 4150]	[15.4, 18.5]	95%
Three-in-series	[3240, 3500]	[14.4, 15.6]	90%
	[3200, 3530]	[14.3, 15.7]	95%

As can be seen the 95% confidence intervals of the population mean lives of the basic element and three-in-series specimen are disjoint, and the former larger than the latter. This implies that these sample means come from separate populations and the basic element has longer life. Table III also lists the 90% and 95% confidence intervals for the basic and three-in-series mean strengths. Here it is seen that the 95% confidence intervals overlap whereas the 90% intervals do not. It can be argued, although not as strongly as in the fatigue case, that the strength results of the basic and three-in-series elements do indeed come from different populations.

Point Estimation, Weibull Distribution

It is well-known that the strength and fatigue life of materials can be best characterized by the log-normal or the Weibull distributions. In this study, the two parameter Weibull distribution is used to represent our results. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) has the form,

$$F(x) = P(X \leq x) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (10)$$

Having collected sample points x , the parameters can be estimated in many ways, for instance, method of moments, maximum likelihood, and regression. In this study the method of linear regression was used to estimate α and β . This technique requires an assignment of numerical values of P_i (called the rank) for each x_i . There are many ways of making this assignment but in this study the median rank method was used. Here the sample points are ordered from lowest to highest and then P_i is assigned by the approximate median rank formula

$$P_i = \frac{i - 0.3}{n + 0.4}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (11)$$

where n is the total number of data points comprising the sample.

In using linear regression, let us transform Eq. (10), by taking the logarithm twice, into the form

$$y' = \alpha x' - \alpha \ln \beta \quad (12)$$

where

$$x' = \ln x \quad (13)$$

$$y' = \ln \ln \left[\frac{1}{1 - P(X \leq x)} \right] \quad (14)$$

At $x = x_i$, the corresponding values of x'_i and y'_i can be evaluated from Eqs. (13) and (14). The quantity y'_i is associated with the theoretical distribution (10), evaluated at x_i . The corresponding value from the approximate rank is given by

$$y_i = \ln \ln \left[\frac{1}{1 - P_i} \right] \quad (15)$$

The difference $y_i - y'_i$, which represents the error, is squared, and summed over i or,

$$\Delta^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y'_i)^2$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \alpha x_i' - \alpha \ln \beta)^2 \quad (16)$$

This sum of the square of errors is then minimized, by forming the two equations $\partial \Delta^2 / \partial \alpha = 0$ and $\partial \Delta^2 / \partial \beta = 0$. Solving these two equations yields the two unknown parameters as

$$\alpha = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2} \quad (17)$$

$$\beta = \exp \left[\frac{\alpha \sum_{i=1}^n x_i - \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \alpha} \right] \quad (18)$$

Table IV gives the values of α and β for the four cases. Values of the mean μ and coefficient of variation are also listed and were obtained from the formulas

$$\mu = \beta \Gamma \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$\text{C.O.V.} = \left[\frac{\Gamma \left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\alpha} \right) - \Gamma^2 \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \right)}{\Gamma^2 \left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \right)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (20)$$

Table IV. Estimated Weibull Parameters for Basic Element and Three-In-Series Specimens

a. Fatigue-Life, Cycles

Specimen	α	β cycles	μ cycles	C.O.V.
Basic Element	1.36	87840	80400	.74
Three-in-series	1.09	25390	24700	.93

b. Static Strength, lbf (kN)

Specimen	α	β lbf (kN)	μ lbf (kN)	C.O.V.
Basic	7.6	4040 (17.97)	3800 (16.90)	.15
Three-in-series	16.2	3740 (15.44)	3360 (14.95)	.06

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness of fit test was used to see how well the Weibull distributions described the data. In all cases the fitted distributions were acceptable at a significance level of 5%.

Fig. 3 presents the Weibull CDF for the fatigue life. The solid curve represents the CDF for the basic element and the dashed curve the three-in-series. The ten data points for the basic element are plotted as x's and the nine data points for the three-in-series are given as open circles. It can be seen that the scatter for both the basic element and three-in-series specimen is large. The Weibull distributions fit the data points fairly well.

Figure 3 Distribution Curves for Compression Fatigue
Data of Graphite/Epoxy Max. Compressive Load
= 74% Basic Element Mean Strength

Figure 4 Distribution Curves for Static Compression Strength
Data of Graphite/Epoxy.
 β , Basic Element Scale Parameter = 4040 lbf (17.97 kN)

Fig. 4 shows the CDF's and data points for the static strength. Once again the solid curve and x's are for the basic element; the dashed curve and open circles give the three-in-series information. The static strength is seen to have much less scatter than the fatigue life.

Looking at the estimated population means we find that the static strength of the three-in-series specimen is 89% of that of the basic element. However, the fatigue life of the three-in-series is only 31% of the basic element. These percentages are seen to be in general agreement with those discussed in the previous section that were calculated from the sample means.

Analysis and Conclusions

From the theoretical analysis, it can be seen that once the distribution of the basic element, Eq. (2) is known, the distribution of the in-series specimen can be calculated from Eq. (3). This is done for both the static strength and the fatigue cases, and the results are presented in Table V. They are also shown in graphical form in Figs. 5 and 6. The calculated ones are labeled "predicted", while the fitted experimental ones are labeled "experimental".

Table V. Comparison of Measured and Predicted Properties of Three In-Series Model

a. Fatigue Case (Large scatter, small shape parameter).

	Basic Element	Three in series	
		Predicted	Measured
Shape Parameter	1.36	1.36	1.09
Mean Life cycles	80400	35900	24700

b. Static Case (Small scatter, large shape parameter)

	Basic Element	Three in series	
		Predicted	Measured
Shape Parameter	7.6	7.6	16.2
Mean Strength lbf (kN)	3800 (16.90)	3290 (14.63)	3360 (14.95)

Figure 5 Predicted and Measured Distribution Curves for Compression Fatigue of Graphite/Epoxy

Figure 6 Predicted and Measured Distribution Curves for Static Compression Strength of Graphite/Epoxy β , Basic Element Scale Parameter = 4040 lbf (17.97 kN)

For the life of the three-in-series specimen we see from Fig. 5 that the shapes of the experimental curve and predicted one are close; however the predicted mean life is 45% higher than the experimental. One possible explanation for this is that the stress distribution is non-uniform along the length of the specimen and the bottom hole is subjected to higher load, and therefore has shorter life than the other two. This is born out by the fact that in the three-in-series fatigue case over 50% of the specimens failed at the bottom hole.

In the case of the static strength the shapes of the experimental and predicted are different, but the mean strengths agree to within 3%.

Based on the results and analysis presented in this report the following conclusions can be drawn,

A. The statistical scatter of strength and life of a basic element is one of the main reasons for the decrease in strength and life for larger structures. In other words, the scale effect in fatigue can be explained by statistical considerations.

B. In general, a large structure contains many small elements which are statistically arranged in a combination of in-series and in-parallel modes. For certain special structures, a simple in-series arrangement can be assumed. In the present case, the three-holed specimen is truly an in-series model, and its life and strength calculated from theory are in good agreement with measured data.

C. The larger the scatter of the strength or life among specimens, or the smaller the Weibull shape parameter, the larger their decrease for large structures due to the scale effect. Since in general there is more scatter in fatigue life than in static strength, the scale effect is more pronounced in fatigue. It is also observed that there is more scatter in fatigue life for graphite composite materials than for metals. Consequently, fatigue data obtained from small composite coupons must be used with caution when applied to larger structures.

Nomenclature

CDF	Abbreviation standing for cumulative distribution function
C.O.V.	Coefficient of Variation
$f(x)$	Probability density function
$F(x)$	Cumulative distribution function
n	Number of elements (as a subscript - the number of elements in series). Also total number of data points in a sample.
$P(X \leq x)$	Cumulative distribution function
P_i	Median rank
s	Sample standard deviation
x	Value of strength or life
x_0	Position parameter
\bar{x}	Sample mean
X	Strength or life of a basic element
X_n	Strength or life of an n in-series element
α	Weibull shape parameter
β	Weibull scale parameter
$\Gamma(z)$	Value of gamma function at z
σ	Population standard deviation
μ	Population mean

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